

Homogeneity testing of china clay by complexometry and spectrophotometry using statistical technique

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Abstract : The use of complexometry and spectrophotometry to determine homogeneity of Al_2O_3 , TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 in china clay suggests that the material may be considered as homogeneous with respect to Al_2O_3 , TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 .

Keywords : China clay, complexometry, homogeneity testing.

Homogeneity testing of china clay¹, the basic ingredient in ceramic body composition, is essential to ensure the quality of the material. The present paper discusses the preparation of homogeneous material and homogeneity testing of the same. Complexometry and spectrophotometry have been used for the determination of Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 present in china clay to test its homogeneity. Use of this material is also valuable for testing, comparison and revision of standard analytical methods.

Experimental

Preparation of sample : About 400 kg of china clay was collected from M/s. Rajmahal Quartz and Kaolim Co. Ltd., Kolkata. The sample was coarse and crushed in a mechanical crusher and the resulting powder was passed through a 0.5 mm sieve. It was further homogenized by stirring the powdered material in a stainless steel drum mechanically for 4 h. The material was then spread out on a polythene sheet on a clean concrete floor and shoveled into a cone. The cone was quartered. Two diagonally opposite quarters were discarded and rest of the material was further crushed. The process was repeated twice. The resulting powder was sieved through a clean stainless steel sieve (-200 + 325 mesh). Proceeding in this way it was possible to prepare 50 kg of powder having a particle size of (-200 + 325 mesh). Ten aliquots each of about 5 g were collected from the different parts of the china clay material after coning and quartering. They were put into acid washed small stoppered glass bottles. These 10 sub-samples were dried at (105–110) °C in an air oven for one hour and kept in the desiccator.

Homogeneity testing of Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 : Ten samples of ~100 mg were taken from each of the two varieties of ten sub-samples and accurately weighed into a platinum cruci-

ble. The samples were fused with a mixture of 1 g of sodium carbonate and sodium tetraborate. The molten mass was dissolved in 5% (v/v) hydrochloric acid and the volume was adjusted to 250 ml with double distilled water. The concentration of Al_2O_3 in the sample solution was determined by complexometry. Spectrophotometry² was applied for determination of Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 using Shimadzu Model 2100 spectrophotometer. Determination of Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 were performed two times for each sample. For each element a one way variance analysis were performed to compare the variability between samples and within samples.

Table 1. Results of variance analysis in respect of Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2

Sample no	Al_2O_3 (% w/w)	Fe_2O_3 (% w/w)	TiO_2 (% w/w)
A1	32.80	0.860	0.235
A2	34.59	0.899	0.240
A3	33.81	0.897	0.230
A4	34.10	0.865	0.229
A5	32.14	0.862	0.234
A6	33.59	0.869	0.239
A7	32.17	0.891	0.233
A8	34.47	0.897	0.236
A9	32.46	0.870	0.240
A10	33.40	0.890	0.240
F (Computed)	1.63	2.18	1.96
F (Critical) $\alpha = 0.05$	3.02	3.02	3.02
Coefficient of variation (%)	2.10	1.23	1.87

These three elements were chosen for the homogeneity control because concentration of Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 play a very significant role in china clay and in order to measure actual Al_2O_3 present, determination TiO_2 is essential.

Statistical treatment of data :

Statistical evaluation of the analytical data for the homogeneity testing of china clay was performed using one way variance analysis³. The estimated variances σ_1^2 (between samples) and σ_2^2 (within samples) significantly differ if the value of $F = \sigma_1^2 / \sigma_2^2$ is higher than the critical value given in the Snedecor's table. Degrees of freedom for σ_1^2 is $(m - 1)$ and that for σ_2^2 is $(n - m)$ where, n = total number of determinations and m = number of samples. The significance level which is chosen for the critical value of F is $\alpha = 0.05$. The coefficient of variations was calculated for each element as the ratio S_{y_i} / y where, S_{y_i} = estimator of the standard deviation of the y_i 's, y_i = mean value of all determinations of the sample i ($i = 10$), y = overall mean and $S_{y_i} = \sqrt{[(\sum(y_i - y)^2) / (m - 1)]}$.

The variability between samples may be due to non-homogeneity of the material and within samples may be due to measurement methods. A comparison of both variances provides indication on the homogeneity of the material with respect to each element under consideration.

Results and discussion

The analytical results of Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 are given in Table 1. Concentrations are expressed in percentage (w/w). For Al_2O_3 , estimator of variance between samples, $\sigma_1^2 = 98.75 \times 10^{-2}$ and estimator of variance within samples, $\sigma_2^2 = 60.44 \times 10^{-2}$. Value of F (calculated) $\sigma_1^2 / \sigma_2^2 = 1.63$. For Fe_2O_3 , the values are, $\sigma_1^2 = 20.92 \times 10^{-4}$, $\sigma_2^2 = 10.67 \times 10^{-4}$ and $F = \sigma_1^2 / \sigma_2^2 = 2.18$ and for TiO_2 , the values are $\sigma_1^2 = 3.42 \times 10^{-4}$, $\sigma_2^2 = 1.94 \times 10^{-4}$ and $F = \sigma_1^2 / \sigma_2^2 = 1.96$. The critical value obtained from the Snedecor's table is $F = 3.02$ for $\alpha = 0.05$. The variance between samples, therefore, does not differ significantly from the variance within samples for all the three constituents under consideration.

Coefficient of variation has also been calculated for all the cases. For Al_2O_3 , overall mean $y = 33.40$, standard deviation of the y_i 's = $S_{y_i} = 0.70$ and the coefficient of variation of the y_i 's = $S_{y_i} / y = 2.10\%$. For Fe_2O_3 , the values are, $y = 0.0879$, $S_{y_i} = 0.011$ and $S_{y_i} / y = 1.23\%$ and for TiO_2 the values are, $y = 0.233$, $S_{y_i} = 0.004$ and $S_{y_i} / y = 1.87\%$. For all the cases the values of coefficient of variations are small. This supports that this material may be considered homogeneous with respect to Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 (at least for sample weight greater than 100 mg).

Conclusion :

The results of variance analysis and the low values obtained for the coefficient of variation for the determination of Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 show that this material may be considered homogeneous with respect to these elements (at least for sample weights greater than 100 mg).

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